

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS OF USING ONLINE PLATFORMS AND APPS FOR COMPREHENSIVE LANGUAGE SKILLS DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation. *The article examines the difficulties and limitations of using online platforms and mobile applications in the process of comprehensive development of students' language skills. Despite the active introduction of digital technologies into the education system, their effectiveness in shaping speaking, listening, reading and writing remains ambiguous. The aim of the study is to identify pedagogical, technical and psychological factors that limit the full development of language competencies when using digital educational resources. The methods of pedagogical observation, questionnaires, comparative analysis of educational results and analysis of students' learning activity using online platforms were used in the work. The results showed that digital tools contribute to the development of lexical and grammatical skills and increase motivation, but they have limitations in the formation of communicative competence, oral speech and stable language skills.*

Keywords: *online learning, digital platforms, language skills, mobile learning, digital education, foreign language.*

Introduction

In the context of global digitalization of society, significant changes are taking place in the education system associated with the active integration of information and communication technologies into the educational process. The development of a digital educational environment has become one of the strategic directions in the modernization of education, aimed at improving the quality of Education, increasing access to educational resources and developing the skills of students of the 21 century. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, these processes are included in the state educational and scientific development programs, where digitalization is considered the main factor in increasing the competitiveness of the education system and preparing students for life in the information society [1].

The change in education through informatization leads to different models of the learning process, such as distance, hybrid and mobile learning. In the context of teaching foreign languages, the use of online platforms, educational applications, and interactive digital resources becomes of strategic importance as they provide access to broad, realistic materials, interactive tasks, and independent language experience opportunities [2]. Researchers emphasize that digital technology is a key factor in the implementation of the principles of individualization of learning, adaptation to the level of training of students and ensuring the flexibility of the learning process [3].

Modern online platforms are effectively used for the integrated development of language skills – reading, writing, listening and speech. Within the framework of the concept of teaching foreign languages with computer support, digital tools are considered as a means of increasing students' internal motivation, automating knowledge Control and significantly expanding opportunities for language Practice [4; 5]. A particularly important aspect is the use of mobile applications that allow students to interact with the language outside the traditional learning environment, contributing to the formation of offline learning skills and a stable language experience [6].

Despite the undeniable advantages of digital tools, their mass adoption has exposed a number of contradictions in pedagogy and methodology. On the one hand, the theory of communicative teaching of foreign languages insists on the importance of direct speech interaction, contextuality of communication and emotional connection between participants in the educational process (7; 8). On the other hand, many online platforms mainly offer test tasks, vocabulary and grammar development,

as well as automatic assessment, which prevents the formation of spontaneous speech and full-fledged communicative competence of students (9; 10).

The problem is becoming particularly acute in Kazakh school practice, where, despite the active introduction of digital technologies, significant discrepancies remain in the technical equipment of educational institutions, the level of digital literacy of teachers and students, as well as in the availability of a stable Internet connection [11]. These factors can become a serious obstacle to the effective use of online platforms and create additional restrictions in the process of learning foreign languages.

It should be noted that most studies are devoted to the advantages of digital technologies, while the issues of their limitations and pedagogical risks, especially in the context of the integrated development of language skills, remain insufficiently studied. Meanwhile, the comprehensive development of language competence presupposes a balanced formation of receptive and productive types of speech activity, which requires not only technological solutions, but also a methodologically sound pedagogical approach [8].

The purpose of the study is to identify the main pedagogical, technical and psychological factors limiting the effectiveness of online platforms and mobile applications in the process of comprehensive development of students' language skills.

There is a noticeable trend towards an increase in the number of online platforms and mobile applications specializing in learning foreign languages. Their attractiveness to users is explained by their ease of access, interactive nature and the ability to personalize the learning pace. The integration of game elements, prompt feedback and automated task verification in digital tools make the language learning process more attractive and efficient. Modern pedagogical research indicates that the use of digital technologies can significantly increase educational motivation and form a positive attitude towards the learning process, which is especially important for middle-aged schoolchildren [5; 6].

Along with this, the issue of the quality of language learning in the context of digital learning is being updated. The methodology of teaching foreign languages is traditionally based on the holistic development of linguistic competence, including phonetic, lexical, grammatical and communicative components [9]. The effectiveness of learning, according to the principles of the communicative approach [7], is determined by the active interaction of students, their participation in dialogical, debatable and situational communication. However, digital platforms do not always have the potential to replicate the natural language environment and ensure full-fledged speech interaction between subjects of the educational process.

Among other things, the automated format of many online assignments helps students focus primarily on identifying the correct answer, while ignoring the need for meaningful use of language tools in authentic communicative contexts. The consequence of this is the development of so-called "test thinking", characterized by fragmented knowledge and insufficient transferability into productive speech activities. Researchers emphasize that excessive use of digital exercises can inhibit the development of critical thinking and creative use of language [10].

Psychological factors play a significant role in students' engagement and learning outcomes. Middle school students often experience difficulties with self-regulation, attention span, and motivation when using digital resources for extended periods, which can affect the effectiveness of online learning [12].

From a methodological point of view, the urgent task is to determine the optimal balance between traditional and digital forms of education. Modern research indicates the high effectiveness of a mixed approach, in which online platforms are used as an additional tool for consolidating the material, and the development of communication skills is carried out in conditions of live interaction in the classroom [13]. This approach makes it possible to overcome the limitations of the digital environment and ensure a more harmonious development of language competencies.

Thus, the relevance of this study is determined by the need for a comprehensive analysis of the advantages and limitations of online platforms in real school practice. Studying these issues will make

it possible to determine the conditions for the effective use of digital technologies and develop methodological recommendations for their integration into the process of teaching foreign languages.

Materials and Methods of Research

The purpose of this work was to identify the obstacles and limitations that arise when integrating online platforms and mobile applications into the integrated development of language competencies of primary school students. The research was conducted within the framework of real educational practice, which provided the collection of empirical data reflecting the practical side of using digital tools in teaching foreign languages.

Participants

The study involved 13 students of grades 6 of secondary school No. 20, aged 11-12 years. All students studied English as part of the compulsory school curriculum and had a comparable initial level of formation of communicative competence. The relevance of choosing this age category is confirmed by studies indicating the increased demands of the digital educational environment on cognitive functions such as self-regulation, attention, and the level of learning motivation. At this stage of learning, students already have a basic vocabulary and elementary grammatical structures, which makes it possible to use digital resources not only for the presentation of new material, but also for its practical consolidation and the development of various types of speech activity.

The research was carried out within the framework of the standard educational process, without making adjustments to the current curriculum. The integration of online platforms and mobile applications into traditional English classes was carried out with the aim of using them as auxiliary didactic tools. This strategy corresponds to the principles of blended learning, which involves the synergy of digital technologies and classical pedagogical methods, rather than their complete replacement.

Digital educational resources were used in the following types of educational activities:

- Implementation of interactive lexical and grammatical exercises.
- Listening to audio materials and then completing listening tasks.
- Working with text materials to develop reading skills.
- Performing written assignments using automatic verification systems.
- Individual self-study of educational material in the homework format.

The use of online platforms provided students with the opportunity to carry out educational activities at an individual pace, receive prompt feedback and repeat the learning material many times. Such opportunities are considered by the scientific community as a significant advantage of computer-mediated foreign language teaching.

The experiment took place in three interrelated blocks:

1. *Diagnostic stage:* The initial level of language skills (reading, listening, writing, speaking) and digital readiness of students were determined through the analysis of academic performance, assignments and observations.

2. *Practical stage:* Online platforms were systematically used in teaching, tracking students' engagement, speed, independence, and difficulties in completing assignments in the classroom and at home.

3. *Analytical stage:* We compared the results, analyzed changes in language skills and identified the features of digital platforms, paying attention to the differences between receptive and productive types of speech.

To increase the reliability of the conclusions, a set of quantitative and qualitative research approaches were applied:

- observing the behavior of students during interaction with digital materials, which helped to identify the characteristic features of their activity;
- student questionnaires aimed at determining the degree of motivation, perceived difficulty of tasks, and personal assessment of the distance learning process;
- study of academic achievements, including checking the correctness of tasks and analyzing changes in academic performance;

- comparative analysis of the effectiveness of the formation of individual language competencies;
- In-depth analysis of the most common mistakes made when working with electronic educational platforms.

The integration of various methodological approaches made it possible to obtain a complete picture of the phenomenon, as well as to compare observational data with actual learning outcomes.

The effectiveness of the implementation of online platforms was assessed using the following indicators:

- formation of vocabulary and grammar skills;
- the level of speech perception by ear;
- the quality of completed written assignments;
- the degree of students' activity in oral communication;
- the level of internal motivation and interest in learning;
- independence in solving learning tasks.

The analysis based on these criteria made it possible to identify both the advantages of using digital tools and the identified obstacles to the full development of language competencies.

Research results

The experiment revealed that the introduction of online resources and mobile applications has a noticeable, albeit contradictory, impact on the formation of comprehensive language competencies in sixth graders. The analysis of data on learning activity, observation of the learning process and the results of the survey allowed us to establish the existence of both advantages associated with the use of digital tools and certain obstacles that manifest themselves in the course of their practical application.

The influence of Internet platforms on the mastery of vocabulary and grammatical norms has become the most pronounced. Interactive tasks with instant feedback and the possibility of repeated repetition contributed to the solid assimilation of vocabulary and the correct application of grammatical models. According to the analysis of the completed works, approximately 80% of the students demonstrated an increase in accuracy in the use of lexico-grammatical units, as well as an acceleration in the performance of exercises.

At the same time, significant disadvantages were identified: when solving creative or productive tasks that require the independent use of language material in spoken or written form, most students faced difficulties. The predominance of the reproductive level of assimilation was revealed — the students successfully coped with the tests in an electronic environment, but they did not know how to adapt the acquired knowledge in real communication situations. These data are consistent with research findings on the preferred development of structural rather than communication skills through digital means.

The use of online resources with audio materials helped to strengthen the skills of listening to speech. Students could repeat audio recordings many times, adapt the level of difficulty to suit themselves, and complete tasks to comprehend key and secondary semantic elements. Observations of the educational process revealed that a significant part of the trainees effectively coped with the tasks of choosing the right option and comprehending the content, demonstrating noticeable progress compared to the initial level of mastery of the material.

At the same time, the insufficient degree of interactivity of the audio tasks made it difficult to develop the skills of retelling what they heard and participating in a free dialogue. Many students rarely turned to the oral form of the answer, which indicates the need to integrate digital materials with live communication practices.

Learning using electronic platforms helped to develop the ability to work with written texts — to find the main and auxiliary information, to use new lexical units and grammatical constructions in a real context. The course participants noted that interactive exercises increased their interest in reading and stimulated independent study of texts.

An analysis of teaching practice showed that students actively used the hints and contextual references offered by the platform to better understand the material. Nevertheless, some students faced difficulties in performing creative tasks related to text analysis and expressing their own point of view, which indicates the limited capabilities of digital systems in the formation of critical thinking when working with written speech.

Platforms with exercises for building sentences, creating short texts, and automatic spell checking had a positive impact on writing development. Students had the opportunity to notice their mistakes and correct them promptly, which contributed to a better understanding of the rules of spelling and grammar.

However, the analysis of written works revealed a tendency to template tasks and unconsciously repeat the studied expressions. The vast majority of students used pre-prepared formulas and a narrow range of grammatical structures, which hindered the formation of the ability to build a free, logically structured written speech. This result indicates the need to combine online exercises with tasks aimed at creative thinking and requiring methodological support from a teacher.

The most serious problems arose when learning oral speech. Despite the availability of audio and video materials, the platforms did not allow for real dialogical contact. According to the pedagogical observation, the students faced difficulties in forming sentences based on the material they had learned and actively participating in the conversation.

The survey showed that 70% of schoolchildren feel anxious when speaking and prefer writing tasks. The lack of immediate feedback and the impossibility of live communication with interlocutors reduced the level of development of free speech and communication skills in everyday conditions.

Table 1. Results of the student survey on the perception of online platforms.

Survey question	Percentage of students, %	Comments / Findings
Do you feel that online platforms help improve your vocabulary and grammar?	80%	Most students reported a positive effect; exercises allow repeated practice
Do you feel confident when completing listening tasks?	68%	Students found it convenient to listen multiple times, but had difficulty retelling what they heard
How easy is it to do writing tasks online?	72%	Positive feedback for automatic corrections, but work is often formulaic
Do you feel confident speaking after using online platforms?	30%	Most students feel insecure; online platforms do not replace real interaction
How interesting are interactive tasks and games?	84%	High motivation and engagement; tasks encourage independent work
Do you get tired or distracted when using platforms for a long time?	60%	Shows mental fatigue and reduced concentration during long sessions

Table 2. The impact of online platforms on the development of language skills of students

Language skill	Effectiveness of online platforms	Main difficulties	Teacher recommendations
Vocabulary & Grammar	High: improves accuracy and speed of exercises	Limited transfer of knowledge to speaking	Use interactive exercises along with speaking practice in class
Listening	Medium-High: improves understanding of spoken materials	Lack of interactivity, difficulty retelling	Add discussion and retelling tasks, pair work

Reading	Medium: develops understanding of texts and information	Difficulties with interpretation and critical analysis	Include analysis, discussion, and creative tasks
Writing	Medium: improves grammar and sentence structure	Formulaic writing, limited creativity	Combine online exercises with creative writing tasks
Speaking	Low: difficulties with spontaneous communication	Insecurity, lack of real interactive communication	Use pair/group oral activities, role plays, dialogues in class
Motivation & Engagement	High: interesting interactive and game-like tasks	Fatigue and distraction during long sessions	Alternate online and offline tasks; control session duration

The use of Internet resources had a stimulating effect on the motivation of students. Interactive tasks, playful materials and visual aids have increased interest in learning English. The students noted the comfort of individual work in an electronic environment - the ability to repeatedly listen to audio tasks, quickly check their own answers and identify errors.

At the same time, certain psychological difficulties were identified. Prolonged learning through platforms provoked decreased attentiveness, increased distraction, and emotional overstrain. Some students faced difficulties in maintaining academic discipline without regular supervision by a teacher, which indicates the importance of methodological assistance and the need to combine distance learning technologies with classical approaches.

The experiment demonstrated that digital platforms and mobile applications are effective in solving the following tasks:

- consolidation of grammatical and lexical knowledge;
- improving the skills of listening comprehension in oral and written form;
- strengthening of internal motivation and development of students' independence.

However, the use of these tools is associated with a number of limitations:

- insufficient level of interaction for the formation of free oral speech;
- the template design of written works;
- the need for constant teacher participation for the full development of all types of speech activity;
- the influence of psychophysiological features - fatigue, absent-mindedness, weak self-regulation.

The data obtained indicate the expediency of a harmonious combination of digital solutions and standard teaching methods, which makes it possible to minimize the disadvantages of online learning and ensure the comprehensive formation of students' language competence.

Conclusion

The results of the study indicate that electronic educational platforms and mobile applications are useful tools in teaching foreign languages, however, the degree of their effectiveness is directly related to the type of skills being studied, the ways of organizing the educational process and the level of pedagogical support.

The experiment demonstrated that digital technologies contribute to the qualitative development of lexical and grammatical knowledge, increase the accuracy of tasks and expand the vocabulary of students. They have a positive effect on the understanding of both oral and written speech due to the possibility of repeated listening to the material, prompt feedback and error correction. Moreover, such platforms enhance the motivation of students, increase their involvement in learning activities, forming an interest in autonomous learning and interactive tasks.

However, certain limitations have been identified. The use of online resources is ineffective in developing the skills of oral speech and free writing - they do not provide a full-fledged communicative practice. Students often show uncertainty in spontaneous communication, and when

writing they tend to mechanically use ready-made formulas. Prolonged work behind the screen leads to overload, decreased concentration, fatigue and distraction, which negatively affects the learning outcome.

Based on the analysis, the following practical recommendations are proposed:

- To use digital platforms as an auxiliary tool, focused primarily on the training of vocabulary, grammar and speech perception skills.
- To improve oral and written speech, complement digital tasks with live forms of interaction: pair exercises, debates, improvisation, creative projects.
- Strategically plan the course of classes, taking into account the age and psychophysiological characteristics of schoolchildren, alternating online and offline elements in order to maintain a high level of attention and motivation.
- To provide methodological guidance and support during the use of digital platforms, helping students apply newly learned vocabulary and grammar in meaningful communicative contexts.

In conclusion, online platforms and applications are effective auxiliary tools in the process of teaching foreign languages. Their capabilities reach the peak of effectiveness when they are competently integrated into a well-designed educational system that combines digital materials with interactive classes under the guidance of a teacher. Such a balanced approach contributes to the formation of comprehensive language competence, increases the independence of students and prepares them for the confident use of a foreign language in real life conditions.

REFERENCES

1. State Program for the Development of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Astana, 2020.
2. Nurgaliyeva, G.K. Informatization of Education in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Almaty, 2015.
3. Sadykova, G.M. Digital Technologies in the Education System of Kazakhstan. Almaty, 2019.
4. Chapelle, C.A. Computer-Assisted Language Learning. Cambridge University Press, 2017.
5. Beatty, K. Teaching and Researching Computer-Assisted Language Learning. Routledge, 2018.
6. Kukulska-Hulme, A. Mobile Learning and Language Teaching. Routledge, 2020.
7. Passov, E.I. Communicative Method of Teaching Foreign Languages. Moscow, 2017.
8. Kunanbayeva, S.S. Theory and Practice of Modern Foreign Language Education. Almaty, 2010.
9. Shchukin A.N. Methodology of Teaching Foreign Languages. Moscow, 2016.
10. Bim, I.L. Theory and Practice of Teaching Foreign Languages. Moscow, 2014.
11. Abdrahmanova, G.K. Digital Education: Problems and Development Prospects in Kazakhstan // Pedagogy and Psychology, 2021.
12. Isabekova, G.B. Psychological and Pedagogical Features of Digital Learning for Schoolchildren // Vestnik KazNPU, 2022.
13. Zhanpeisova, M.M. Modular Technology of Teaching. Almaty, 2016.